

ELEPHANT

IN THE LAB

SHORT ANALYSIS

Et alia mille

Short title	Et alia mille
Long title	On average, the 20 highest performing authors in Physics and Astronomy have more than 1200 coauthors per article.
Authors	Martin Schmidt ¹ , Benedikt Fecher ¹ , Christian Kobsda ¹
Author affiliation	¹ Knowledge Dimension, Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society, Berlin, Germany
Author bios	<p>Martin Schmidt is a doctoral researcher at the Institute of Landscape Systems Analysis within Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research and associate researcher at Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society.</p> <p>Benedikt Fecher is the programme director of the research programme Knowledge Dimension and heads the Open Science research group at the Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society.</p> <p>Christian Kobsda works as the political consultant at the Leibniz Association and is an associate researcher at the Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society.</p>
Author social links	Martin Schmidt: ORCID – ResearchGate – Twitter Benedikt Fecher: ORCID – ResearchGate Christian Kobsda: ORCID – ResearchGate
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Description

The number of authors per article in the subject area *Physics and Astronomy* is 1268 on average with a maximum of 5154 authors in one paper (ATLAS Collaboration et al., [2015](#)). The mean number of coauthors is increasing by 58 per year in the respective time period (Figure 1). The articles in this analysis ($n = 2135$) were cited 27 times on average.

NUMBER OF AUTHORS PER ARTICLE IN THE SUBJECT AREA PHYSICS AND ASTRONOMY

Increase of co-authors per year = 58
Number of articles = 2135

Figure 1: [Boxplot](#) of the number of authors per paper in the subject area *Physics and Astronomy*. The box denotes 25–75% of the values with the median (bold line) in it. The small circles are outliers. The yellow line shows a linear model of the mean number of authors per article with a confidence interval of 0.95 shown in light grey. Data source: Scopus. CC BY 4.0 Schmidt, Fecher, Kobsda.

Methodology

The results of the Advanced search in Scopus were restricted by an algorithm with

- a time period of publishing (2010 to 2016)
- the document types (articles or reviews),

- and a quantitative limitation regarding the publication output (articles by the 20 highest performing authors with the most Scopus listed articles in every subject area).

For details and code see Schmidt et al. [2017](#).

References

ATLAS Collaboration, CMS Collaboration, Aad, G., Abbott, B., Abdallah, J., Abdinov, O., ... Woods, N. (2015). Combined Measurement of the Higgs Boson Mass in pp Collisions at and 8 TeV with the ATLAS and CMS Experiments. *Physical Review Letters*, *114* (19), 191803. [Link](#).

Schmidt, M., Fecher, B., Kobsda, C. (2017). Methodology for the analysis of authors meta data using the Scopus data base. *Elephant in the lab*. [Link](#).